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2 **Simulation of medicanes over the Mediterranean Sea in a regional climate model ensemble:**
3 **impact of ocean-atmosphere coupling and increased resolution**

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10
11 **Abstract**

12 Medicanes are cyclones over the Mediterranean Sea having a tropical-like structure but a rather small size, that can
13 produce significant damage due to the combination of intense winds and heavy precipitation. Future climate projections,
14 performed generally with individual atmospheric climate models, indicate that the intensity of the medicanes could
15 increase under climate change conditions. The availability of large ensembles of high resolution and ocean-atmosphere
16 coupled regional climate model (RCM) simulations, performed in MedCORDEX and EURO-CORDEX projects,
17 represents an opportunity to improve the assessment of the impact of climate change on medicanes. As a first step
18 towards such an improved assessment, we analyze the ability of the RCMs used in these projects to reproduce the
19 observed characteristics of medicanes, and the impact of increased resolution and air-sea coupling on their simulation.
20 In these storms, air-sea interaction plays a fundamental role in their formation and intensification, a different
21 mechanism from that of extra-tropical cyclones, where the baroclinic instability mechanism prevails. An observational
22 database, based on satellite images combined with high resolution simulations (Miglietta et al. 2013), is used as a
23 reference for evaluating the simulations. In general, the simulated medicanes do not coincide on a case-by-case basis
24 with the observed medicanes. However, observed medicanes with a high intensity and relatively long duration of
25 tropical characteristics are better replicated in simulations.

26
27 The observed spatial distribution of medicanes is generally well simulated, while the monthly distribution reveals the
28 difficulty of simulating the medicanes that first appear in September after the summer minimum in occurrence.
29 Increasing the horizontal resolution has a systematic and generally positive impact on the frequency of simulated
30 medicanes, while the general underestimation of their intensity is not corrected in most cases. The capacity of a few
31 models to better simulate the medicane intensity suggests that the model formulation is more important than reducing
32 the grid spacing alone.

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34 A negative intensity feedback is frequently the result of air-sea interaction for tropical cyclones in other basins. The
35 introduction of air-sea coupling in the present simulations has an overall limited impact on medicane frequency and
36 intensity, but it produces an interesting seasonal shift of the simulated medicanes from autumn to winter. This fact,
37 together with the analysis of two contrasting particular cases, indicates that the negative feedback could be limited or
38 even absent in certain situations. We suggest that the effects of air-sea interaction on medicanes may depend on the
39 oceanic mixed layer depth, thus increasing the applicability of ocean-atmosphere coupled RCMs for climate change
40 analysis of this kind of cyclones.

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1. Introduction

Medicanes (Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones) are a particular kind of cyclones that are observed sporadically over the Mediterranean Sea. Their diameter is rather small, typically less than 300 km and they generally present a symmetrical cloud structure around a cloudless eye (Fita et al. 2007) , which indicates tropical characteristics like a warm core and a predominant role of air-sea fluxes and convection in their development and maintenance. They form from baroclinic cut-off lows, evolving into a warm core cyclone through tropical transition (Emanuel 2005; Chaboureau et al. 2012) . Medicanes can produce considerable damage due to the combination of intense winds and heavy precipitation. Observed cases of tropical-like cyclones in the Mediterranean region have been analyzed in detail (Pytharoulis et al. 2000; Reale and Atlas 2001; Homar et al. 2003; Moscatello et al. 2008) .

Cyclones with partial tropical characteristics occur in other basins of the world as well. For example, subtropical cyclones have been observed in the Atlantic Ocean (Guishard et al. 2009; Evans and Braun 2012; González-Alemán et al. 2015) and in the Pacific Ocean (Garde et al. 2010) . There is no clear-cut separation between tropical and extratropical cyclones. Hart (2003) developed a classification method, the cyclone phase space analysis, in which the different cyclone types form a continuum, and transitions between extra-tropical and tropical cyclones are smoothly integrated. Medicanes can attain fully-tropical characteristics during their lifetime, but this tropical phase is generally rather short (Miglietta et al. 2013) .

The small size of medicanes and the sparse data available over the sea, where they develop, complicate the analysis of their climatological characteristics. Reanalysis data are too coarse for detecting and characterizing medicanes adequately. This has led to the use of satellite data as the main way for obtaining databases of medicanes (Tous and Romero 2013). Miglietta et al. (2013) combined satellite data and high resolution limited area meteorological model simulations to identify additional aspects of medicanes such as their warm core structure and high low-level wind speed. A long-term climatology has been derived by Cavicchia et al. (2013) through dynamical downscaling of six decades of reanalysis, applying a regional climate model (RCM) with spectral nudging. The spatial distribution of medicanes is very similar in these climatologies, with two maxima over the Western Mediterranean and the Ionian Sea, respectively. This distribution differs clearly from that of the most frequent extratropical Mediterranean cyclones. The seasonal distribution shows the highest activity in autumn and winter, while very few medicanes are seen during summer, despite the high sea surface temperature (SST) in this season. The frequency of medicanes depends on the selection criteria, ranging from 0.5 to about 1.5 medicanes per year in the three databases mentioned above.

In the frame of the impacts of climate change on tropical cyclones, an important issue is whether areas that support now only marginally the development of tropical cyclones, like the Mediterranean Sea, will experience an increase of tropical cyclone activity in the future. A potential result of anthropogenic climate change is the poleward extension of the effects of tropical cyclones (Walsh et al. 2016). The latitude at which tropical cyclones reach their maximum intensity has already shifted poleward during the last decades (Kossin et al. 2014). In this context, the future variations of medicane characteristics due to climate change are a matter of concern. RCMs have been used to downscale global climate model (GCM) scenarios (Gaertner et al. 2007; Cavicchia et al. 2014; Walsh et al. 2014) . Romero and Emanuel

81 (2013) applied a statistical-deterministic method for increasing the medicane sample size. Tous et al. (2016) used a
82 high resolution global climate simulation to analyze future medicane changes. A consistent result is a reduction in the
83 frequency of medicanes under future climate conditions, together with an intensity increase for the most intense
84 medicanes.

85
86 For the climatological analysis of medicanes, dynamical downscaling with RCMs has some advantages. This technique
87 can produce high resolution results, which are fundamental for representing medicanes, and can include feedbacks that
88 can affect their development, like the impact of ocean-atmosphere coupling. Considering that air-sea coupling generates
89 typically a negative feedback on the intensity of tropical cyclones, through vertical mixing of the oceanic column
90 (Emanuel 1999) , we could expect a similar intensity reduction on medicanes, at least for the most intense cyclones.
91 The coupling takes into account that deeper cold water can be brought to the surface, reducing the sea surface
92 temperature and, as a consequence, the latent and sensible heat fluxes to the atmosphere, which play a key role in the
93 intensification of medicanes. The analysis of the effect of air-sea coupling on medicane simulation is one aim of the
94 present study. This kind of analysis has been performed previously by Akhtar et al. (2014) , which used only one
95 atmospheric model coupled to a simplified 1-D ocean model, while here we use a multi-model ensemble of simulations
96 with 3-D ocean models.

97
98 Here we analyze the ability of RCMs to simulate medicanes, using a large multi-model ensemble of RCM simulations
99 from EURO-CORDEX (Jacob et al. 2014) and Med-CORDEX (Ruti et al. 2015) projects. Though GCM
100 simulations, with a similar resolution as the RCM simulations used here, are also available, these GCM simulations are
101 not adequate for the present study due to several reasons. There are only few such high-resolution GCM runs. These
102 GCM simulations have been performed without coupling to the ocean and typically cover only short time periods,
103 which is not appropriate here due to the large interannual variability of the medicane frequency. Finally, such GCM runs
104 are not part of coordinated multi-model experiments, in contrast to the RCM simulations used here. The use of many
105 different models represents an advance with respect to previous medicane simulation studies, and allows us to consider
106 the uncertainty linked to differences in model formulation. EURO-CORDEX and Med-CORDEX ensembles are
107 particularly valuable for the analysis of medicanes, as they include high resolution (up to 10 km) and atmosphere-ocean
108 coupled runs. This will allow us to assess the impact of increased resolution and air-sea coupling on the simulation of
109 medicanes in RCMs. The present analysis is part of a broader effort to obtain an improved assessment of the effects of
110 anthropogenic climate change on medicanes. In this respect, the use of EURO-CORDEX and Med-CORDEX
111 simulations is also advantageous, as they include a very large number of future climate projections using the same
112 RCMs analyzed here.

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115 **2. Method and data**

116

117 We have used a total of 29 simulations from the Med-CORDEX and EURO-CORDEX projects, all nested in ERA-
118 Interim reanalysis, with the exception of AWI simulations which have been nested in ERA-40 reanalysis and cover a
119 much bigger domain, including the Atlantic tropical region. The following list indicates the institution acronym,
120 followed by the RCMs used. The most relevant information for the purposes of the paper is included in brackets

121 (coupled or uncoupled RCM; horizontal resolution in km), and the simulation periods are also shown:

122

- AWI/GERICS: REMO (uncoupled; 50, 25 and 18 km) and ROM (coupled; 50, 25 and 18 km (Sein et al. 2015)). Simulation periods: 1982-2001 (50 km runs), 1978-2001 (25 km runs), 1975-2001 (18 km runs)
- CNRM: ALADIN5.2 (uncoupled; 50 and 12.5 km (Colin et al. 2010; Herrmann et al. 2011)) and RCSM4 (coupled; 50 km (Sevault et al. 2014)). Simulation periods: 1979-2011 (ALADIN5.2 runs), 1980-2011 (RCSM4 run)
- ENEA: REGCM (uncoupled; 25 km (Artale et al. 2010)) and PROTHEUS (coupled; 25 km (Artale et al. 2010)). Simulation period: 1982-2010.
- GERICS: REMO (uncoupled; 50 and 12.5 km (Jacob et al. 2012)). Simulation period: 1989-2008.
- GUF: CCLM 4-8-18 (uncoupled; 50 and 10 km (Rockel et al. 2008; Kothe et al. 2014)). Simulation period: 1989-2008
- IPSL-INERIS: WRF (uncoupled; 50 and 12.5 km (Vautard et al. 2013)). Simulation period: 1989-2008
- IPSL: WRF3.1.1 (uncoupled; 50 km (Skamarock et al. 2008; Flaounas et al. 2013; Stéfanon et al. 2014)) and WRF3.1.1-NEMO (coupled; 50 km (Brossier et al. 2015)). Simulation period: 1989-2008
- KNMI: RACMO22E (uncoupled; 50 and 12.5 km (Meijgaard et al. 2012)). Simulation period: 1989-2008
- MET(Office): HadGEM3 (uncoupled; 50, 25 and 12.5 km (Moufouma-Okia and Jones 2014)). Simulation period: 1990-2010
- SMHI: RCA4 (uncoupled; 50 and 12.5 km (Kupiainen et al. 2011; Samuelsson et al. 2011)). Simulation period: 1980-2010
- UCLM: PROMES (uncoupled; 50, 25 and 12.5 km (Domínguez et al. 2010; Domínguez et al. 2013)). Simulation period: 1989-2008

123

124 As the aim of this study is to analyze the impact of high resolution and air-sea coupling on the simulation of medicanes,
125 we have grouped the simulations into pairs of low/high resolution simulations and pairs of uncoupled/coupled
126 simulations with the same atmospheric RCM. Multi-model ensembles of such simulation pairs are then used for the
127 evaluation of the RCM ability to simulate medicanes. The different simulations are identified by combining the
128 acronyms of the institution and the model plus the horizontal resolution in km (e. g., AWI-REMO-50).

129

130 The cyclone detection and tracking method of Picornell et al. (2001) is applied for detecting cyclones. This method is
131 designed particularly for mesoscale cyclones, and is therefore especially suited to the detection of medicanes. The
132 detection of lows is based on sea level pressure (SLP), and wind at 700 hPa is used as an auxiliary variable for the
133 tracking. The cyclone intensity is represented by the daily maximum surface wind, calculated within a radius of 400 km
134 from the cyclone center. Only cyclones exceeding tropical storm intensity (17.5 m/s surface wind speed) are considered.

135

136 As medicanes have tropical characteristics, we can identify them by using the cyclone phase space (CPS) method of
137 Hart (2003) , by which a cyclone is classified as tropical if it is thermally symmetric (it has no frontal structure) and
138 has a full-tropospheric warm core. These features are measured by 3 parameters: B , $-V_T^L$ and $-V_T^U$, derived from the
139 geopotential values between 900 and 300 hPa. B represents the horizontal thermal symmetry of the cyclone, with

140 positive values above 10 m indicating an asymmetric (frontal) cyclone, and values below that threshold indicating a
141 symmetric (non-frontal) cyclone. The thermal wind parameters for the lower troposphere ($-V_T^L$) and the upper
142 troposphere ($-V_T^U$) describe the warm or cold core structure of the cyclone. Positive values indicate a warm core and
143 negative values a cold core. Due to the small diameters of medicanes, we have applied the CPS criteria around a radius
144 of only 150 km from the low pressure center. The CPS method is a compact and objective way to represent the 3D
145 structure of a cyclone and detect if it has tropical characteristics.

146
147 Taking into account the huge amount of data to analyze and the highly time-consuming methods applied, we have
148 limited our analysis to the months with higher medicane frequency. Medicanes appear more frequently in autumn and
149 winter, so we have focused our analysis on the months from August to January. For the same reason, and also because
150 some fields necessary for our analysis were not available at 6-hourly time resolution, we use daily average values of the
151 different variables, instead of 6-hourly values. This has the side effect of not allowing the calculation of the B parameter
152 for cyclones lasting only 1 day. A sequence of at least two low centers is needed to identify the displacement direction
153 necessary for calculating B. Due to this limitation, we have not considered the B parameter for selecting tropical
154 cyclones.

155
156 The medicane database developed by Miglietta et al. (2013) , covering the 1999-2012 period, has been used as
157 reference for evaluating the simulation results. In this database, observed medicane cases selected through satellite
158 images are simulated with a high resolution model, and only those cyclones showing a fully tropical structure for at
159 least 6 h are considered as medicanes. This criterion has been adapted for comparison with the daily data used here. For
160 daily average data, a cyclone is considered to be a medicane if $-V_T^L > 0$ (lower warm core) and $-V_T^U > -10$ (upper warm
161 core or nearly warm core). The latter value is a threshold selected in order to classify as medicanes also those cyclones
162 that have an upper warm core lasting for less than 1 day. In the following, the location of the medicanes corresponds to
163 the points where the cyclones reach their maximum intensity in the phase with tropical-like characteristics.

164
165 In order to illustrate how the CPS method represents the tropical characteristics of medicanes and their formation
166 mechanism, we show in Fig. 1 the specific case of the medicane observed in November 2011. Using 6-hourly data from
167 the operational ECMWF analysis, the evolution of the cyclone in the cyclone phase space is shown in the upper panel of
168 Fig. 1. The cyclone begins as a cold-core extratropical low and experiences a tropical transition, acquiring a full-
169 tropospheric warm core. In this case, the medicane maintained a tropical structure during more than two days. The
170 effect of using daily average data is shown in the lower panel of Fig. 1. The evolution of the cyclone is clearly more
171 limited than for 6-hourly data, as the daily average values indicate a hybrid structure in the first day (with a lower-
172 tropospheric warm core and upper-tropospheric cold core), and the maximum values of the thermal wind parameters are
173 smaller (indicating a less intense warm core during the fully tropical phase). However, the daily values are sufficient to
174 detect the tropical structure of the medicane, supporting their use in the present study.

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177 **3. Results and discussion**

178

179 **3.1 Simulation of observed medicanes**

180

181 The tropical transition, responsible for the generation of medicanes, is a very complex mechanism, as shown for
182 example by Davis and Bosart (2004) or Moscatello et al. (2008) . It depends on synoptic features (an upper level cut-
183 off low, vertical wind shear), on local air-sea interactions and on small-scale processes (convection developing around
184 the location of the low and liberating latent heat) that are parameterized in climate models. This combination of factors
185 makes the simulation of tropical transitions a challenging issue. It is not clear whether climate-mode simulations can
186 reproduce in a deterministic way the observed medicanes, as no reinitialization of atmospheric fields is done in the
187 domain interior after the beginning of the simulation. Medicanes form well within the model domains, which means that
188 their tropical characteristics are not directly transmitted through the lateral boundary conditions.

189

190 In order to analyze the correspondence between simulated and observed medicanes, we have compared their dates and
191 locations. Some margin has been allowed in this comparison, so that simulated medicanes found within 10° of the
192 observed location, or up to two days before or after the observed medicanes (if they form under the same cut-off low)
193 have been considered as corresponding to the same case.

194

195 Table 1 shows the set of high-intensity medicanes (maximum surface winds above 25.5 m/s) and Table 2 the set of
196 moderate-intensity medicanes (maximum surface winds between 17.5 and 25.5 m/s) registered in the reference database
197 from Miglietta et al. (2013) . The cases in which the RCMs indeed simulate a medicane are indicated in red. There are
198 rather few full matches between the two sets, as can be seen in Tables 1 and 2. This confirms a previous result obtained
199 by Walsh et al. (2014) using one RCM, in which most of the simulated medicanes did not correspond to observed
200 cases. They pointed to the stochastic processes dominating the formation of such small-size cyclones as a reason for this
201 result.

202

203 In our study, there are additional possible reasons for the absence of correspondence between simulations and
204 observations. The duration of the phase with tropical characteristics in the observed cases is generally limited to a few
205 hours, which is below the time resolution available in the simulation outputs considered here. In this respect, it is
206 noteworthy that medicanes with a longer persistence of tropical features are more frequently reproduced in the
207 simulations. The medicane in December 2005 (reproduced as a warm-core cyclone by five simulations) had a tropical
208 structure during 33 h, and reached maximum 10 m winds of 33 m/s, while the medicane in November 2011 had a
209 tropical phase of 63h, and maximum 10 m winds of 32 m/s. The latter case is reproduced by all three available
210 simulations (CNRM) as a medicane, as shown by the CPS analysis in Fig. 2. The evolution in the cyclone phase space
211 compares really well with the results from the ECMWF reanalysis shown in Fig. 1. Even the two lower resolution
212 simulations with CNRM models are able to detect a fully tropical structure for 2 days. The November 2011 medicane
213 shows a remarkable reproducibility, compared to the other storms. No other simulation reached the year 2011, so this
214 case cannot be analyzed using other models.

215

216 A clear factor affecting the simulation of medicanes is their intensity. Lower-intensity medicanes (Table 2) are not
217 replicated by most models. More coincidences between simulated and observed medicanes are found for higher-
218 intensity medicanes (Table 1). Davis and Bosart (2004) distinguish two types of tropical transition, depending on the
219 amplitude of the precursor disturbance: in transitions originated by strong extratropical cyclones, wind-induced surface
220 heat exchange (WISHE; Emanuel (1987)) is the key process, while in cases where the precursor is a weak
221 extratropical cyclone, this extra-tropical disturbance is an organizing factor for the convection, which must then
222 experience self-organization to generate a self-amplifying cyclone. This could explain in part the different degree of
223 reproducibility of some medicanes: the two cases cited above, which are better reproduced by the models, correspond to
224 strong and large upper-level cut-off lows. In contrast, the medicane in September 2006 formed under a comparatively
225 weak disturbance, and is not reproduced in most simulations. The cases coincident in simulations and observations
226 show no preference for a particular model configuration or resolution.

227
228 There are several possibilities for the missed simulation of an observed medicane. The tropical transition could be only
229 partially simulated, resulting in a hybrid cyclone with a lower-tropospheric warm core and upper-tropospheric cold
230 core. Also, the simulated cyclone could maintain its original cold-core structure, or might not reach the threshold of
231 17.5 m/s (maximum surface wind) used in our detection method. We have examined these possibilities. Simulated
232 cyclones with a hybrid structure are shown in grey, and simulated cyclones with a cold-core are marked in blue in
233 Tables 1 and 2. An empty cell indicates that no cyclone with intensity above 17.5 m/s has been simulated.

234
235 Hybrid and cold-core cyclones are simulated much more frequently in cases of high-intensity observed medicanes than
236 of moderate-intensity observed medicanes. It is clearly more likely that models simulate a cyclone corresponding to an
237 actually observed medicane if the latter is intense. The case of IPSL-WRF311, which employs spectral nudging, is
238 revealing in this aspect. All high-intensity medicanes are replicated by this model as cold-core, hybrid or warm-core
239 cyclones; but only one out of five less intense medicanes is captured by it. The same happens with MET-HadGEM3-12
240 simulation. This behaviour is likely associated to the general underestimation of intensity in the simulations. Observed
241 medicanes with intensity above 25.5 m/s are generally simulated as cyclones with intensities below this threshold, and
242 observed medicanes with intensity between 17.5 and 25.5 m/s do not reach the 17.5 m/s threshold in many simulations.
243 Another factor contributing to this model deficiency could be the smaller size of the less intense observed medicanes,
244 which limits the ability of the models to capture them. But the lack of clear differences between low and high resolution
245 simulations in Tables 1 and 2 suggests that this is not a major factor.

246
247 The ability of models to simulate at least partially tropical characteristics also seems to depend on the intensity of
248 observed medicanes. Table 1 includes more hybrid and warm-core cyclones than cold-core cyclones in the simulations.
249 The opposite comes out for the less intense medicanes, as a large majority of the simulated cyclones in Table 2 show a
250 cold core.

251
252 The simulation domain is another factor affecting the reproduction of observed medicanes. The set of AWI/GERICS
253 simulations stands out from the rest, as very few of the observed medicanes are detected in them. This is likely related
254 to the domain used in those runs, which is much bigger than in other simulations and covers the whole Atlantic tropical
255 area. The differences with the other REMO simulations are also likely due to differences in the domain extension, as

256 GERICS-REMO uses the (much smaller) EURO-CORDEX domain. An additional reason for the deviating results of
257 AWI/GERICS runs could be that it is nested in ERA40 instead of in ERA-Interim reanalysis.

258
259 On the other hand, the models simulate medicanes that do not coincide in date with the observed ones, but occur in
260 favorable environments for their development. A visual examination of the synoptic setting for several simulated intense
261 medicanes indicates that they typically appear under observed cut-off lows. The different models also simulate different
262 cases. These facts indicate that medicanes have a clear stochastic component, and the evaluation of their simulation in
263 climate models should be made statistically. Hereafter we analyze several statistical measures for them.

264 265 **3.2 Impact of increased resolution**

266
267 In order to adequately consider the effect of horizontal resolution on the simulation of medicanes, first we should take
268 into account how the resolution affects the cyclone intensity. As we are dealing with tropical-like cyclones, we will use
269 the criteria presented by Walsh et al. (2007) for obtaining a resolution-dependent threshold for tropical storms, which
270 have maximum surface winds above 17.5 m/s. Winds in tropical cyclones reach a maximum at a relatively small
271 distance from the cyclone center, decreasing rapidly with increasing distance. Therefore, if we sample the winds using a
272 larger grid spacing (coarser resolution), a smaller wind maximum will be simulated. Following Walsh et al. (2007) ,
273 for the resolutions used in the present study, the threshold values for tropical storm intensity are 16.5 m/s (for a 50 km
274 grid spacing) and 17.5 m/s (for a 12.5 km grid spacing). The application of the same method for hurricane intensity
275 (33.5 m/s, corresponding to 65 knots) yields the curve of Fig. 3. The threshold values for this intensity are 31 m/s (for
276 50 km) and 33.5 m/s (for 12.5 km). Therefore, intensities of 16.5 m/s and 31 m/s in the low resolution simulations are
277 respectively equivalent to intensities of 17.5 m/s and 33.5 m/s in high-resolution runs. Equivalent values for other
278 intensities are obtained through a linear interpolation between those values.

279
280 Fig. 4 (upper panel) shows the yearly frequency of medicanes for the different low/high resolution pairs of simulations
281 using the same model (most of them have 50/12.5 km grid spacings). There is a clear frequency increase with
282 resolution, which is systematic (all models show it) and generally strong (in six out of ten models, the frequency
283 increases nearly two times or more). Whereas most of the low resolution simulations underestimate the observed
284 frequency of about 1 medicane/year found in our reference database (and even more the value of 1.5 medicanes/year in
285 Cavicchia et al. (2013)), the high resolution simulations show an improvement, with values generally nearer to the
286 observed value. There is a large spread among models, with appreciable overestimations and underestimations of the
287 observed frequencies.

288
289 Regarding the effect of resolution on cyclone intensity, we have clustered the distribution in two groups (moderate
290 intensity: 17.5-25.5 m/s, and high intensity: above 25.5 m/s). The small number of medicanes in many simulations
291 hinders the use of percentiles, obtained directly from the simulated values, for analysing intensity changes. Fig. 4 (lower
292 panel) shows the number of high-intensity medicanes per year for each pair of low/high resolution runs. The reference
293 database gives a value of about 0.5 high-intensity medicanes per year. The strong underestimation of high intensity
294 medicanes in the 50 km simulation (with values between 0 and 0.2 medicanes per year) is not corrected by many of the

295 high-resolution simulations. Only three high-resolution simulations show a strong increase of high-intensity medicanes.
296 The average simulated intensity (not shown) confirms the difficulties of most models in reproducing high intensity: the
297 negative bias found in low resolution simulations (the observed value is of about 27 m/s, while the simulated values lie
298 between 19 and 22 m/s) is not appreciably improved by the increase in resolution in most of the models. Intensity
299 changes seem to be strongly model-dependent, and increased resolution alone does not improve the intensity of the
300 simulated medicanes.

301
302 The spatial distribution of medicanes is shown in Table 3. In the reference database, the highest number of medicanes is
303 found in the central area (around Italy and to the south of it), followed by the western area. The lowest number of
304 medicanes is detected over the eastern Mediterranean. Other observed databases like that of Tous and Romero
305 (2013) show similar spatial locations. The RCMs reproduce well the eastern minimum, and on average the high
306 resolution runs improve the distribution between the western and central Mediterranean areas. The north-south
307 distribution is well captured by both low and high resolution simulations. An important aspect of observed medicanes is
308 that their distribution is clearly displaced to the south when compared to the spatial distribution of all Mediterranean
309 cyclones, which has a strong maximum around the Gulf of Genoa. The distribution of simulated medicanes also
310 reproduces well this displacement to the south with respect to the typical baroclinic cyclones.

311
312 Table 3 also shows the monthly distribution of medicanes. The reference database shows a clear autumn maximum
313 (September and October), while the percentage of winter medicanes is smaller than in the simulations. However, the
314 appearance of January medicanes in the simulations is similar to that observed in other climatologies like Tous and
315 Romero (2013) or Cavicchia et al. (2013). Differently from the reference database, the latter climatologies include
316 also the 1990's and the 1980's and thus cover all the years analyzed in the simulations. An increase in the relative
317 percentage of winter medicanes is found with higher resolution.

318
319 It can also be seen in Table 3 that the observed high percentage of September medicanes is not well captured by the
320 models. No improvement is found in that respect in the high resolution runs. Model formulation seems to be more
321 important than resolution for the representation of these medicanes, as only a few models are able to simulate them
322 better. The difficulties of models in the representation of September medicanes probably depend on their intensity, as
323 they are generally among the least intense medicanes (as can be seen from their division in Tables 1 and 2). The
324 intensity of the baroclinic disturbance originating them is also frequently weaker than in other autumn or winter months,
325 which could complicate their successful simulation.

326

327 **3.3 Impact of ocean-atmosphere coupling**

328

329 The frequency of medicanes for the pairs of coupled/uncoupled runs is presented in Fig. 5 (upper panel). No clear
330 frequency change is found between them: the changes are generally small and of differing signs. The effect of coupling
331 on the number of high-intensity medicanes can be seen in the lower panel of Fig. 5. Some tendency towards a lower
332 number of intense medicanes is found in coupled simulations, but changes are rather small. Thus the hypothesis that air-
333 sea interaction in the coupled runs can produce a negative feedback is not clearly confirmed. The low resolution of

334 several models could be a reason for the lack of clear changes. Akhtar et al. (2014) found that coupled runs improved
335 the simulation of medicanes in the case of high resolution (about 10 km), but not for lower resolutions. The general
336 underestimation of intensity in simulated medicanes can also limit the effect of coupling, as its effect should be stronger
337 for higher intensities of cyclones (and more intense air-sea exchanges).

338
339 Aggregate values presented before, like the frequency and intensity statistics, might be hiding information about the
340 underlying mechanisms of development. Interesting results are found if we separate the medicanes spatially and
341 temporally. Fig. 6 shows the number of medicanes per year north and south of 38N. The changes in the northern part of
342 the Mediterranean Sea depend on the model. But the variations in the southern part of the Mediterranean Sea are more
343 systematic: five of the six simulations simulate less medicanes in this area in the case of coupled runs. The only
344 exception is the ENEA coupled simulation, in which a strong increase of medicanes is simulated in the southern part.
345 Relative values shown for the ensemble mean in Table 3 indicate also an overall reduction of medicanes in the southern
346 part in the coupled simulations.

347
348 Table 3 shows another remarkable result: the relative monthly distribution of medicanes shows a distinct reduction of
349 autumn medicanes and a corresponding increase of winter medicanes in the coupled runs. The strongest change occurs
350 for January medicanes, with an increase from 24% in the uncoupled runs to 33% in the coupled runs. There is even a
351 rise in the absolute number of January medicanes for ENEA-PROTHEUS and AWI-ROM coupled models. On the other
352 hand, the absence of September medicanes is not corrected by the use of coupling.

353
354 The opposite changes in autumn and winter medicanes in the coupled runs might be related to the oceanic mixed layer
355 depth. As shown by D'Ortenzio (2005), the Mediterranean mixed layer is very shallow in summer, and reaches the
356 maximum depth in winter. Mixed layer depth can control the magnitude of the negative intensity feedback due to air-sea
357 coupling. If the oceanic mixed layer is shallow, cold waters from below the mixed layer will be lifted to the surface due
358 to air-sea interaction, reducing the SST. But if the mixed layer is deep, the emerging deeper water will maintain
359 basically the same SST, limiting or canceling the negative feedback. There are even cases where the air-sea feedback
360 can be positive (Shay et al. 2000). Significantly, medicanes are not observed in summer, despite the higher SST
361 values. They appear in autumn, when SSTs decrease but the mixed layer depth increases, or in winter, when SSTs are
362 low but the mixed layer depth is at its maximum.

363
364 In order to clarify the impact of coupling and the possible influence of the oceanic mixed layer depth, we have looked in
365 more detail at two individual simulated cyclones that show opposite behaviour with respect to the effect of coupling on
366 simulated intensity. The simulated cyclones are taken from the CNRM-ALADIN52/RCSM4 pair of simulations. The
367 first case is a cyclone simulated in December 1996: the uncoupled run generates a rather intense cyclone (23 m/s of
368 maximum surface wind) with a full-tropospheric warm core, while the coupled run strongly reduces strongly the
369 intensity of the cyclone. This can be well observed in the mean sea level pressure maps for 9 December 1996 of Fig. 7
370 (uncoupled run in the upper panel, coupled run in the lower panel). The SSTs under the cyclone centers (represented
371 through shaded circles) show noticeable differences in both runs. At the beginning of the track, the SST is slightly
372 higher (0.3 °C) in the coupled run than in the uncoupled run, but for the last represented track point (when the cyclone
373 reaches its maximum intensity) the SST is clearly lower (1.2 °C) in the coupled run. The simulated SSTs in the coupled

374 run (Fig. 8, upper panel) show a complex mesoscale structure. Particularly, the lowest SSTs are not found right at the
375 northern coast (as in the uncoupled run), but further south, precisely under the track of the simulated cyclone in the
376 coupled run. The intensity differences due to the coupling can be well explained by the SST differences, as the cyclone
377 in the uncoupled run moves over warmer waters. The mixed layer depth for the coupled run is shown in the lower panel
378 of Fig. 8. The low SST values at the end of the track coincide with an area of low values of the mixed layer depth. The
379 mixed layer depth shows also a high spatial variability. A rather good overlap can be seen between the spatial
380 distribution of SST and mixed layer depth in the coupled run, as relatively low values of SST correspond to low values
381 of the mixed layer depth.

382
383 The second case corresponds to January 1980. A medicane appears in the coupled simulation, but not in the uncoupled
384 run as the warm core criteria are not met there. The intensity is higher in the coupled run (25.4 m/s of maximum surface
385 wind) than in the uncoupled run (21.8 m/s). The location of the cyclone is similar in both runs, as shown in Fig. 9, but
386 there are important differences in the SSTs, with clearly higher values (1 °C) in the coupled run at the beginning of the
387 track. The comparatively warm water north of Algeria in the coupled run extends under a significant part of the track of
388 the cyclone (see Fig. 10). Mixed layer depth values are generally higher than for the first case, and they show again an
389 interesting overlap with SST features: the relatively high SST tongue north of Algeria coincides with an area of deep
390 mixed layer. The two opposite cases indicate that the coupling can act differently depending on the distribution of SST,
391 and that the mixed layer depth might have some effect on mesoscale SST features.

392

393

394 **4. Concluding remarks**

395

396 In the context of the impacts of climate change on tropical cyclones, an important issue is whether areas that now
397 support only marginally the development of tropical cyclones, like the Mediterranean Sea, will experience an increase
398 of tropical cyclone activity in the future. A poleward extension of the effects of tropical cyclones is a potential result of
399 global warming. Previous studies of climate change projections, based generally on individual atmospheric models,
400 have indicated that medicanes (Mediterranean tropical-like cyclones) could increase in intensity in the future. Large
401 ensembles of high resolution and ocean-atmosphere coupled regional climate model (RCM) simulations are now
402 available from MedCORDEX and EURO-CORDEX projects, representing an opportunity to update and improve the
403 assessment of the impact of climate change on medicanes. As a first step towards such an improved assessment, we
404 analyze the ability of the RCMs used in these projects to reproduce the observed characteristics of medicanes, and the
405 impact of increased resolution and air-sea coupling on their simulation.

406

407 Medicanes are generated through tropical transition, which is a complex process including factors over a wide range of
408 scales, from synoptic-scale upper level cut-off lows to small-scale convection. This complexity raises the following
409 issue: can observed medicanes be reproduced in climate-mode simulations on a case-by-case basis? We have examined
410 if the RCMs replicate the observed medicane cases through comparison with an observational-numerical database.
411 Results indicate that in most cases, models generate medicanes at dates that are not coincident with actual medicanes.
412 There are some exceptions to this, suggesting that the likelihood that an RCM replicates an actual medicane is higher
413 when the observed medicane has a long tropical phase and is intense. In agreement with the existence of two different

414 types of tropical transition, suggested by Davis and Bosart (2004) , the intensity of the precursor baroclinic disturbance
415 also seems to be important for the reproduction of observed medicanes. This may explain in part the difficulties of
416 RCMs for simulating September medicanes, as these medicanes originate typically from relatively weak cut-off lows.

417
418 There are several reasons why an actual medicane is not replicated by RCMs: a hybrid cyclone with a partially tropical
419 structure is sometimes simulated, or the simulation maintains the cold core structure of the initial cyclone. In some
420 cases, the simulated cyclones do not reach the minimum intensity (17.5 m/s) required for their detection. There is a
421 general underestimation of medicane intensity, which is well illustrated by the case of a model applying spectral
422 nudging: all high-intensity observed medicanes (with a maximum surface wind above 25 m/s) are reproduced by it as
423 cyclones with wind speed above 17.5 m/s, but most lower-intensity cases are not detected in these simulations. The
424 absence of coincidence (on a case-by-case basis) between climate simulations and observations can be expected due to
425 the complicated genesis and structure of medicanes and their small size, and has been observed in previous studies
426 (Walsh et al. 2014) . As a consequence, the evaluation of medicanes in long regional climate model simulations
427 (without reinitialisation of the atmospheric fields) should be done statistically.

428
429 Pairs of low and high resolution runs and pairs of uncoupled and coupled runs have been compared to analyze the
430 impact of resolution and coupling on the simulation of medicanes. The use of increased resolution shows a systematic
431 and generally strong impact on the frequency of medicanes. Higher frequency is simulated when the grid spacing is
432 reduced, representing an improvement in most cases. But unexpectedly, the negative bias in the intensity of medicanes
433 is not corrected by most higher-resolution runs. The intensity seems to depend more on the model formulation than on
434 resolution alone.

435
436 For tropical cyclones in other basins, air-sea interaction frequently produces a negative feedback on the intensity of
437 cyclones, as the enhanced vertical mixing in the ocean under strong winds transports colder deep water to the surface.
438 But if the oceanic mixed layer below the cyclone is deep, the negative feedback is inhibited. The lack of a clear overall
439 effect of coupling on the frequency or intensity of the simulated medicanes might be due to the influence of such
440 contradicting factors. A hint in this direction is provided by the detailed analysis of two specific cyclones, and the
441 distinct seasonal shift of medicanes in the coupled simulations from autumn to winter supports this explanation. The
442 negative feedback should be clearer for medicanes in September, when the mixed layer is very shallow, but only a small
443 number of September medicanes have been simulated by the models. This could be a further reason for the limited
444 effect of coupling.

445
446 The possible influence of the oceanic mixed layer depth on the interaction between medicanes and the sea should be
447 analysed in a detailed way in future studies. But in case it is confirmed, it could have important consequences for the
448 future evolution of medicanes, as projections of the Mediterranean mixed layer depth show important future changes,
449 which depend on the emissions scenario (Adloff et al. 2015) . This would increase the utility of applying ocean-
450 atmosphere coupled RCMs for climate change studies.

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TABLES:

	17-18/10 2003	3-6/11 2004	13-15/12 2005	26/9 2006	26/10 2007	4/12 2008	6-8/11 2011
AWI/GERICS-REMO-18							X
AWI/GERICS-ROM-18							X
AWI/GERICS-REMO-25							X
AWI/GERICS-ROM-25							X
AWI/GERICS-REMO-50							X
AWI/GERICS-ROM-50							X
CNRM-ALADIN52-12	Blue		Grey			Blue	Red
CNRM-ALADIN52-50	Blue		Grey			Blue	Red
CNRM-RCSM4-50	Blue		Grey			Blue	Red
ENEA-REGCM			Grey				X
ENEA-PROTHEUS	Blue		Red				X
GERICS-REMO-12			Red			Blue	X
GERICS-REMO-50			Blue		Red	Blue	X
GUF-CCLM4-10	Blue	Red	Blue			Blue	X
GUF-CCLM4-50						Blue	X
INERIS-WRF-12			Blue				X
INERIS-WRF-50			Grey			Grey	X
IPSL-WRF311	Grey	Blue	Red	Grey	Blue	Grey	X
IPSL-WRF311-NEMO	Grey	Blue	Red	Grey	Blue	Grey	X
KNMI-RACMO22E-12	Grey	Blue	Grey			Blue	X
KNMI-RACMO22E-50	Blue		Grey			Blue	X
MET-HadGEM3-12	Grey	Grey	Grey	Blue	Blue	Blue	X
MET-HadGEM3-25		Grey	Grey		Blue	Blue	X
MET-HadGEM3-50		Grey	Grey		Blue		X
SMHI-RCA4-12			Grey				X
SMHI-RCA4-50							X
UCLM-PROMES-12	Red		Grey	Grey			X
UCLM-PROMES-25	Blue	Grey	Red			Grey	X
UCLM-PROMES-50	Blue		Grey	Grey		Blue	X

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Table 1: Coincidences between simulated cyclones and observed high-intensity medicanes (maximum winds > 25.5 m/s). Colors indicate the type of simulated cyclone: red indicates a warm-core, grey a hybrid and blue a cold-core cyclone. The dates are taken from Miglietta et al. (2013). The “X” indicates that year 2011 was not included in the simulation period of the corresponding models.

	13/09 1999	10-11/09 2000	9/10 2000	21/09 2004	17/10 2007
AWI/GERICS-REMO-18					
AWI/GERICS-ROM-18					
AWI/GERICS-REMO-25					
AWI/GERICS-ROM-25					
AWI/GERICS-REMO-50					
AWI/GERICS-ROM-50					
CNRM-ALADIN52-12					
CNRM-ALADIN52-50					
CNRM-RCSM4-50					
ENEA-REGCM					
ENEA-PROTHEUS					
GERICS-REMO-12					
GERICS-REMO-50					
GUF-CCLM4-10					
GUF-CCLM4-50					
INERIS-WRF-12					
INERIS-WRF-50					
IPSL-WRF311					
IPSL-WRF311-NEMO					
KNMI-RACMO22E-12					
KNMI-RACMO22E-50					
MET-HadGEM3-12					
MET-HadGEM3-25					
MET-HadGEM3-50					
SMHI-RCA4-12					
SMHI-RCA4-50					
UCLM-PROMES-12					
UCLM-PROMES-25					
UCLM-PROMES-50					

Table 2: As in Table 1, but for moderate-intensity observed medicanes (maximum winds between 17.5 and 25.5 m/s).

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	Spatial distribution (%)					Monthly distribution (%)					
	West	Center	East	North	South	Aug.	Sep.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.	Jan.
Reference database	33	50	17	67	33	0	33	33	17	17	0
Low-resolution ensemble mean	52	33	15	67	33	1	4	25	33	19	18
High-resolution ensemble mean	42	45	13	64	36	1	5	17	34	22	21
Uncoupled ensemble mean	39	47	14	59	41	1	1	17	34	23	24
Coupled ensemble mean	47	41	12	65	35	1	2	10	26	28	33

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Table 3: Left part of the table: relative spatial distribution of medicanes (percentage of total medicanes) from August to January. Zonal division in 3 areas: Western Mediterranean ($10^{\circ} < \text{lon} < 24^{\circ}\text{E}$), Central Mediterranean ($10^{\circ}\text{E} < \text{lon} < 24^{\circ}\text{E}$) and Eastern Mediterranean ($\text{lon} > 24^{\circ}\text{E}$). Meridional division in 2 zones: North ($\text{lat} > 38^{\circ}\text{N}$) and South ($\text{lat} < 38^{\circ}\text{N}$). Right part of the table: monthly distribution of medicanes (percentage of total medicanes) from August to January. The results are shown for the ensemble means of low/high resolution runs and uncoupled/coupled runs.

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FIGURES:

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648 Figure 1: Cyclone phase space (CPS) analysis for the observed medicane of November 2011, calculated for 6-hourly
649 (upper panel) and daily mean (lower panel) geopotential values of the ECMWF operational analysis. The two
650 parameters represented in the diagram are $-V_T^L$ (lower-tropospheric thermal wind parameter, indicating a lower-
651 tropospheric cold core if it has negative values and a lower-tropospheric warm core if it has positive values) and $-V_T^U$
652 (upper-tropospheric thermal wind parameter, indicating an upper-tropospheric cold core if it has negative values and an
653 upper-tropospheric warm core if it has positive values). Extratropical cyclones are represented in the lower left
654 quadrant, while tropical cyclones are represented in the upper right quadrant. The cyclone track is indicated in red in the
655 upper left inset of the panels. The beginning of the cyclone evolution in the CPS is indicated through an “A”, while the
656 end is indicated through a “Z”.

691 Figure 2: CPS diagrams as in Figure 1, for the same medicane case of November 2011, but for daily mean values of the
 692 uncoupled CNRM-ALADIN52 simulation at 50 km resolution (upper panel), uncoupled CNRM-ALADIN52 simulation
 693 at 12 km resolution (middle panel) and coupled CNRM-RCSM4 simulation at 50 km resolution (lower panel).

Figure 3: Windspeed threshold (m/s) for hurricane-force wind detection as a function of model resolution (km).

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Figure 4: frequency of medicanes (cyclones per year) (upper panel) and frequency of high-intensity medicanes (above 25.5 m/s) (lower panel) for pairs of lower resolution (red bars) and higher resolution simulations (green bars).

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Figure 5: As in figure 4, but for pairs of uncoupled (red bars) and coupled (green bars) simulations.

Figure 6: Number of medicanes per year, north of 38N (upper panel) and south of 38N (lower panel), for pairs of uncoupled and coupled simulations.

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923 Figure 7: Simulated cyclone of 9 December 1996 in the uncoupled run (CNRM-ALADIN52-50; upper panel) and in the
 924 coupled run (CNRM-RCSM4; lower panel). The contours show mean sea level pressure (hPa) when the simulated
 925 cyclone reaches its maximum intensity. The shaded circles show sea surface temperature (°C) for consecutive 6-hourly
 926 cyclone center locations from the first location over sea (labeled with an "A") to the location of the maximum intensity
 927 (labeled with a "Z").
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Figure 8: Simulated cyclone of 9 December 1996 in the coupled run (CNRM-RCSM4). Sea surface temperature (°C) and oceanic mixed layer depth (m). The cyclone track is superimposed, using the same labeling as in Figure 5.

1034 9: As in figure 7, but for the simulated cyclone of 15 January 1980.

1033 Figure

1085 Figure

10: As in figure 8, but for the simulated cyclone of 15 January 1980.

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